

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№6(1)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 564 sahifa,
1-iyun, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyuu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Milliy xarakter tushunchasining pedagogik va aksiologik talqini.....	10
Usmonova Muattar Bahadirjonovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning o'zini o'zi anglashida muloqotning o'rni	14
Yaxshiboyeva Zuhra, Pardayeva Munisa	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning zamonaviy usullari	17
Dilsora Shodmonova	
Педагогические предпосылки развития билингвизма у детей в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях	24
Истамова Нигора Азимжановна	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida neyrogimnastika texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari.....	29
Saidova Nigora Olimovna, G'ulomova Shaxnoza Abdusalom qizi	
Jismoniy tarbiya va sport: iqtidorli yoshlarni tanlash, saralash va ularni maqsadli tayyorlashning zamonaviy yo'llari.....	32
Muxamedjanov Shovkat Muxrumovich	
Yoshlar ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasida tarixiy xotira, milliy meros va qadriyatlardan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari.....	36
Nomozov Muhammadyusuf Meyliqul o'g'li	
Sport tashkilotlarida rahbarlik qilish va boshqarish.....	40
Artikov Xayrulla Baxtiyarovich	
Formation and Development Stages of Terminology as a Scientific Discipline	44
Lola Mannobova	
Lexicographic Features of Onomastic Units in English and Uzbek Dictionaries	48
Berdiyeva Mashhura Tulqin qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining qobiliyat, qiziqish va o'rganish usullarini hisobga olgan pedagogik metodlar va dars rejaları	51
Abdullaeva Gulmira, Egamberganova Yorqinoy Ollobergan qizi	
Disputning ingliz romanlaridagi pragmatik va lingvokulturologik ko'rinishlari	55
Abdumalikova Diyoraxon Rafiqjon qizi	
O'yin texnologiyalarining aqliy rivojlanishida muammolari bo'lgan bolalar ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	59
Abdunazarov Abdumutal Olimovich	
Auditoriyada va auditoriyadan tashqari jarayonda talabalar ijtimoiylashuvini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	64
Alimova Gulrux Farhod qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kreativ fikrlashni rivojlantirishda interaktiv o'yin texnologiyalarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari	70
Axtamova Mohinur O'tkir qizi	
Oilaviy zo'ravonlikka uchragan ayollarni qo'llab-quvvatlashda mahalla va ijtimoiy xizmatlarning o'rni	74
Dumarova Gulfira Kozimbekovna, To'Iqinova Muxlisaxon Jamshid qizi	
O'zbek milliy romanchiligida tarixiy haqiqat va badiiy talqin (Xayriddin Sultonning "Yaldo kechasi" romani misolida)	78
G'aybulloyeva Parvina Samandar qizi	
Aqli zaif bolalarda kommunikativ faoliyatning ontogeneza shakllanishi	82
Hamraqulova Durdona Dilshod qizi	
Neuroeducation va Phygital Learning asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kognitiv faolligini rivojlantirish metodikasi	87
Hikmatova Yulduz Nuritdinovna	

Autizm spektri buzilgan bolalarning ijtimoiy-pedagogik moslashuvining nazariy asoslari	91
<i>Shodmanxojiyeva Iroda Ne'matulla qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutq rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashda o'yin texnikalarining roli	95
<i>Jamolova Farida Fatillo qizi</i>	
Ta'lim qardosh tillarga yo'naltirilgan mtt direktorining boshqaruv kompetentligini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari (Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi misolida)	98
<i>Jumagulova Gulziya Madiyarovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda talabalarning raqamli taqdimot va ommaviy nutq ko'nikmalarini axborot texnologiyalari vositasida takomillashtirish	103
<i>Junaydullayev Oxunjon Kaxorjon o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida o'yin texnologiyalari orqali nutq malakalarini rivojlantirish	107
<i>Maqsuda Maxsudovna Murodova</i>	
O'zbek tilida "nur" so'zining ko'chma ma'nolari	113
<i>Maxbuba Axatova</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarini kasbiy tayyorlashda raqamli texnologiyalar va interfaol metodlardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	116
<i>Misirova Nodira Tovbayevna, Nosirova Dilfuza Sa'dullayevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ingliz tilida og'zaki nutqini shakllantirishdagi qiyinchiliklar	120
<i>Nabiyeva Xilola Abdulmuratovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ma'naviy-ma'rifiy qiyofasini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari...	123
<i>Niyozova Maftuna Normaxmat qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida "Tarbiya" fanini tabiiy fanlar bilan integratsiyalash asosida ekologik tafakkurni shakllantirish.....	126
<i>Norbo'tayeva Iroda Yunusovna</i>	
Suzish vositalari yordamida talabalarning qo'l va oyoq mushaklarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	130
<i>Nosirov Sardor To'lqinjon o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning metakognitiv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	134
<i>Nosirova Ra'no Xamidovna</i>	
Dual ta'limda oliy ta'lim va maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning mazmuni.....	137
<i>Qoraboyeva Zohidaxon To'lanboyevna, Tursunbayeva Sevara Abdullo qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalar nutqida noverbal vositalarning roli.....	142
<i>Qurbanova Surayyo Tuynazar qizi, Maqsudboyeva Dilbar Olimjon qizi</i>	
Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda integrativ yondashuvning pedagogik zarurati va nazariy asoslari	146
<i>Qurbonmurotov Eldor Abdusaidovich</i>	
O'zbekistonning zamonaviy ta'lim muhitida o'zbek-rus bilingvizmi sharoitida o'quvchilar nutqining psixolingvistik xususiyatlari.....	149
<i>Qurdasheva Bonu Bexzod qizi</i>	
Xorij olimlari tadqiqotlarida prosotsial xulq-atvor namoyon bo'lishining o'rganilishi	153
<i>Rahimova Sarvinoz Odilboy qizi</i>	
Musiqqa fanlarini o'qitishda inquire-based learning texnologiyasidan foydalanish metodlari.....	157
<i>Raximova Dilbar Rizakulovna</i>	
Maktab rahbarining qaror qabul qilish uslubi pedagogik jamoa ijtimoiy faolligini rivojlantirish omili sifatida..	161
<i>Raximova Maryam O'tkir qizi</i>	
Yosh sportchilarda yurak-qon tomir tizimining morfofunksional adaptatsiyasi va sportchi yuragi fenomeni..	173
<i>Alimova Nasiba Adxamovna</i>	
Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyotda turizm klasterlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	179
<i>Kurbonova Kamola Ilxomovna</i>	
Nutq madaniyati va notiqlik san'ati	183
<i>Mamadaliyeva Lola Shailyasovna</i>	
Molekulyar fizikada klasster yondashuvi asosida masalalar yechish samaradorligini oshirish	188
<i>Mirzamuratov Baxodir Fayzullayevich</i>	
Oliy o'quv yurtlari, sport tashkilotlari va sport marketingi tashkilotlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning zarurati.....	192
<i>Samatov Javlonbek Abdukayumovich</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini texnologiya darslarida turli materialdan amaliy ishlarni tashkil qilish metodikasi	195
<i>Sanakulov Xamrakul Rizakulovich, O'roqova Nigina Botirjon qizi, Xoliqulova Ozoda Shuxratovna</i>	
Modern Teaching Methods in English Language Learning.....	199
<i>Sarvinoz Abdulhakimova</i>	
Erkin Vohidov ijodining o'rganilishi	202
<i>Shahnoza Muhammadiyeva</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida nutqiy faoliyatni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	205
<i>Shopulatova Nasiba Umirovna</i>	
Yuqori intensivlikdagi atsiklik yuklamalar ta'sirida futbolchilar organizmi funksional holatining yoshga oid xususiyatlari.....	208
<i>Shukurova Sayyora Sa'dullaevna, Kadirov Abdurashid</i>	
Talabalarda badiiy did va estetik tarbiyasini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	211
<i>Temirov Murodjon Anvarovich</i>	
The Role of Authentic Materials in Teaching English for Specific Purposes: Implications for Tourism Students.....	215
<i>Toshmamatova Marjona Olimjon kizi</i>	
Neyrokognitiv rivojlanish va bolalarning maktabga psixologik tayyorgarligi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik	220
<i>Toshpo'latova Mahina Farxod qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda terminologik tafakkurni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari	224
<i>Umaraliyeva Shahlo Sayfullo qizi</i>	
Artistic Pedagogy as a Basis for Developing Spiritual-Communicative Culture in Student Youth: Pedagogical Foundations	228
<i>Umarova Malika Khisabidinovna, Orifjonova Kamolabonu Kozimbek qizi</i>	
Pragmatic Competence and Cultural Adaptation in EFL Contexts: Challenges and Pedagogical Implications.....	232
<i>Veronica Khatamova</i>	
Ta'lim tojik tilida olib boriladigan maktablarda morfologiya o'qitish muammosi	236
<i>Xojiyeva Iroda Zokirjon qizi</i>	
Innovatsion yondashuv asosida "Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni tabiat bilan tanishtirish" modulini o'qitish metodikasi muammo sifatida	240
<i>Zaxro Yo'ldashovna Shanasirova</i>	
Interaktiv topshiriqlar orqali boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining chet tiliga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini individuallashtirish	246
<i>Nishonova Gulchehra Ravshanjon qizi</i>	
The Role of Project-Based Learning and Artificial Intelligence Technologies in Enhancing Foreign Language Students' Academic Achievement and Motivation.....	250
<i>Olimov Sh. Sh., Zaripov K. Ya.</i>	
Mechanisms for Assessing Academic Achievements in the Finnish Education System and the Possibility of their Adaptation In Schools In Uzbekistan	254
<i>Saytbekova Svetlana Saylaubaevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda bolalar bilan innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida ekologik omillarni singdirish	257
<i>Xoldorova Mashxura G'ulomovna</i>	
Finlyandiya ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilarning o'zlashtirishini baholash mexanizmlari va ularni O'zbekiston maktablarida qo'llash istiqbollari.....	260
<i>Xudaybergenova Zuxra Isakovna</i>	
Jadidchilik harakati va uning pedagogik-ijtimoiy mohiyati hamda tamoyillari	263
<i>Yusupov Ma'mur Ma'rufovich</i>	
Проблемы нравственного воспитания личности в произведениях В. Распутина.....	269
<i>Рахимова Шахзода Равшановна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matematik kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik omillari	273
<i>Imamova Nasiba Xurramovna</i>	

Bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilarida tolerantlik madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	276
<i>Xidirov Faxriddin Fozilovich</i>	
Транслингвальные практики русскоязычных мигрантов в условиях многоязычной среды	280
<i>Рахмонова Нилуфар Уткир кизи</i>	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarda leksik-grammatik komponentni diagnostika qilish metodlari	284
<i>Mamatkulova Lobar Tolibjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'yin texnologiyalari asosida bolalarning ta'limiy faoliyatini rivojlantirish.....	288
<i>Norqulova Ma'mura Husniddin qizi</i>	
Nutqdagi fonetik kamchiliklarning o'quv faoliyati va savodxonlikka ta'siri	293
<i>Xikmatova Saboxat Xusniddinovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda sog'lom psixologik muhitni shakllantirish omillari	296
<i>Xusanbayeva Ziyoda Maxmutdjon qizi</i>	
Social-Psychological Factors of Increasing the Quality of Life	300
<i>Abdullaeva Ranazhon Matyakubovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiruvchi zamonaviy o'quv topshiriqlarini ishlab chiqishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	307
<i>Abdumalikova Gulchiroy</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tayanch hayotiy va fanga oid kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	311
<i>Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna, Sayfullayeva Dilnoza Amrullayevna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tili darslarida madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	316
<i>Azimova Maftuna Azizbekovna</i>	
Talabalarda lingvistik kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	321
<i>Eshbekova Dilnoza Ibraimovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarida moslashuvchanlikning psixologik xususiyatlari	324
<i>Fayziyeva Gulhayo Erkin qizi, Fatullayeva Manzura Idillo qizi</i>	
Naim Karimov talqinida Oybek badiiy tafakkurining biografik manbalari	327
<i>Jonpo'lotova Gulshoda Qobil qizi</i>	
Kurashchilarning kuch sifatini rivojlantirishda maxsus mashqlardan foydalanish	334
<i>Muxamedjanov Umidulla Fayzullayevich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda axloqiy idealni shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik asoslari	337
<i>Saidova Malika Erkin qizi</i>	
Yengil atletika texnikalarini pedagogik mahoratni rivojlantirish metodikalarida qo'llash	340
<i>Sattarov Qarshiboy Narqulovich, Mirzayev Karim Mamarasul o'g'li</i>	
Yengil atletika mashg'ulotlarida shug'ullanuvchilarning tezkorlik va chidamlilik sifatlarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion metodikasi	344
<i>Sattarov Sardor Sunnatulloevich</i>	
Innovatsion rivojlanish asosida uzluksiz ta'limning integratsiyalashgan mazmunini modellashtirish metodologiyasi.....	348
<i>Umarov Lutfillo Murodilloyevich</i>	
Milliy maktablarda rus tilini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim resurslari va veb-saytlardan foydalanish metodikasi....	352
<i>Xolmirzayeva Munira Jahongir qizi</i>	
Педагогические основы повышения профессиональной компетентности будущих преподавателей физического воспитания высших образовательных учреждений	357
<i>Мавлянов Бахром Сангирович</i>	
Раннее выявление и мониторинг кожных заболеваний с помощью искусственного интеллекта: интегрированные архитектуры, алгоритмы и перспективы клинического внедрения	361
<i>Э. Ш. Назирова, Ш. Б. Абдусаломова</i>	
Ingliz tilida modallikni ifodalash vositalari va ularning semantik xususiyatlari	368
<i>Abdujalilova Sarvinov Rashid qizi, Abdurazzokova Mehriniso Azimjon qizi</i>	

MUNDARIJA	СОДЕРЖАНИЕ	CONTENTS
	Ona va farzand munosabatlarida etnomadaniy omillarning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	373
	<i>Abdullayeva Dilbar Ubaydullayevna</i>	
	O'quvchilarning gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda interaktiv metodlarning o'rni	378
	<i>Abdurahmanov Muhammadjon G'ulomjonovich</i>	
	Aralash ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida ta'lim jarayonini loyihalashning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	381
	<i>Alibayev Sobir Xolboyevich</i>	
	Formativ baholash jarayonidan foydalanib o'quvchilarning o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshirish	386
	<i>Amirkulova Dilnoza Zokir qizi</i>	
	Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni kasbiy-pedagogi faoliyatga tayyorlash tendensiyalari	389
	<i>Artikbayeva Aziza Abror qizi</i>	
	The Role of National Values in English and Uzbek Literature: a Comparative Study	392
	<i>Ataniyazova Sohiba Xamidovna</i>	
	Frans Kafka ijodining psixologik talqini.....	396
	<i>Atayev Shukur-Ali Ayub-Aliyevich</i>	
	Development of a Set of Health-Promoting Exercises for Middle-Aged Men 50-60 Years Old, Taking Into Account Physical Training	400
	<i>Dehqonova Mahmuda Ortiqovna</i>	
	Oliy ta'limda talabalarni jismoniy rivojlantirish metodikalari	404
	<i>Imomov Asliddin Abdurazoqovich, Sattarov Qarshiboy Narqulovich</i>	
	Современные мобильные технологии: эволюция и развитие.....	408
	<i>Жураев Илхом Исхокович</i>	
	Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kongruentlik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning mazmuni	413
	<i>Kamalova Dilobar Tairovna</i>	
	Methodology for Developing Communicative Competence of Future Teachers Based on Multimedia Tools.....	418
	<i>Kudratova Sultonposhsha Otabek qizi, Khalilova Mukhlisa Ulug'bek qizi, Ziyotova Umida Otabek qizi</i>	
	Raqamli ta'lim muhitida ona tili darslarida matn bilan ishlashni tashkil etish.....	423
	<i>Erdanova Zamira Olimovna</i>	
	Milliy sport turlari orqali talaba yoshlar bilan interfaol dars jarayonini tashkil etish.....	426
	<i>Mirzayev Az'am Xudaynazarovich, Sattarov Qarshiboy Narqulovich</i>	
	Pedagogika bitiruvchilarining kasbiy o'zini o'zi rivojlantirishga asoslangan barqaror bandligini ta'minlash modeli.....	430
	<i>Omonova Mohiniso Maqsud qizi</i>	
	Boshlang'ich ta'limda fanlararo integratsiyani sun'iy intellekt asosida takomillashtirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	435
	<i>Panjliyev Jo'raqul Menglimamat o'g'li</i>	
	Boshlang'ich ta'limda web-kvest topshiriqlardan foydalanish.....	440
	<i>Saidova Gavhar Ergashovna, Itolmasova Oygul Sabritdinovna</i>	
	Developing Communicative Competence in English Language Education Through Modern Interactive Methods.....	443
	<i>Sativoldieva Shoxsanam Utkir qizi</i>	
	Анализ современных подходов и их недостатков к совершенствованию методов повышения пропускной способности в разветвлённых оптических сетях связи	447
	<i>Киямов Рахматулло Рузиевич</i>	
	Психологические механизмы профилактики противоправного поведения несовершеннолетних (на примере Республики Казахстан)	452
	<i>Тайтелиева Ақтолқын Битуқызы</i>	
	Professional ta'lim muassasalarida o'quvchilarning stressga bardoshlilikini rivojlantirishning pedagogik modeli	459
	<i>Islamova Fotima Shamsiddinovna, Aliqulova Nilufar Jumanazar qizi</i>	
	The Importance of Developing an Exercise Complex for Preparing Para Armwrestlers for Competition.....	463
	<i>Karimov Faxriddin Xurramovich</i>	

Loyiha asosidagi ta'limda portfolio va baholash rubrikalari tizimi: boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kommunikativ kompetensiyani monitoring qilish.....	467
Maxmudova Zulxumor Alim qizi	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilar uchun mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish modeli	472
Muqimova Zulxumor Ziyataliyevna	
Methods for Developing Labor Productivity Through Increasing the Physical Activity of Enterprise and Organization Employees	477
Muxametov Axmad Muxametovich	
Developing Learner Autonomy Through Peer and Self-Assessment In EFL Classrooms.....	481
Rakhmonova Nodirakhon Mukhammadjonovna	
Oilaviy muhitning bolalar shaxsiy rivojlanishiga psixologik ta'siri	488
Xidoyatova Layli To'xtasinovna, Xursanova Mashhura Bobir qizi	
Tarbiyasi og'ir o'smirlarda ijtimoiy adaptatsiya va shaxslararo munosabatlar xususiyatlari.....	493
Elov Ziyodulla Sttorovich, Muxammadiyeva Gavhar Sirojiddin qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida nutq madaniyatini shakllantirishning ilmiy-nazariy masalalari va pedagogik shartlari.....	499
Nasriddinova Nasiba Alimjonovna	
Ingliz va o'zbek lug'atlarida frazeologik birliklarning berilishi va lug'atlardagi muammolar	505
Oqboyeva Zulfiya Bobonazarovna	
Gamifikatsiya texnologiyasi asosida talabalarning o'quv motivatsiyasini rivojlantirish	510
Yuldashev Sardarxon Rashitxon o'g'li, Sattarova Maftuna Ravshan qizi	
Argumentativ tuzilmalar va sintaktik modellar: aktiv/passiv konstruksiyalar va nominalizatsiya hodisasi	513
Utupova Oysapar Urazmatovna	
Yoshlarni sog'lomlashtirish jarayonida milliy va xalq o'yinlaridan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari...	516
Axmedov Gayratjon Kosimovich	
Introduksiya sharoitida dorivor valeriana (<i>Valeriana officinalis</i> L.) ning suv rejimi, biokimyoviy tarkibi va ildiz hosildorligi	522
Xamrayev Rashid Ravshan o'g'li, Omonova Dildora Uchqun qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni savod o'rgatishga tayyorlashda zamonaviy pedagogik va raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning metodik asoslari.....	527
Go'zal Qurbonova	
Shaxmat mashg'ulotlari orqali talabalarda tafakkur va qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	532
Kulboyev Nodirjon Salaydinovich	
Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarining deontologik kompetensiyasiga oid G'arb pedagogik tafakkurining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	535
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li	
Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda TIMSS yondoshuvining ahamiyati.....	539
Xoldorova Shahnoza Ismatjon qizi	
Zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida lingvokulturologik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish	544
Barotova Gulhayo Farhod qizi	
Uy ta'limidagi imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning ijtimoiy-psixologik moslashuvi va ta'lim sifati monitoringi tahlili.....	548
Tojimatova Gavxarxon G'ulomjonovna, Pulatova Gulnoza Murodilovna	
O'quvchilarda tarixiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishda multimedia texnologiyalarining didaktik imkoniyatlari	554
Muhammadiyev Javlon Hayitboyevich	
Muammoli ta'lim asosida o'quvchilarda geografik bilimlarni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	558
Yovqochev Furqat Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Geografiya ta'limida 4k ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion usullari.....	561
Yuldasheva Oyjamol Davronbek qizi	

DEVELOPING LEARNER AUTONOMY THROUGH PEER AND SELF-ASSESSMENT IN EFL CLASSROOMS

UDK: 378.091.3:811.111

Rakhmonova Nodirakhon Mukhammadjonovna

English teacher, secondary school No. 41,
Oltiariq district, Fergana region<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-8925-8668>

Abstract: This article explores the role of peer and self-assessment in fostering learner autonomy in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. Learner autonomy has become a central objective in modern language education, emphasizing students' ability to take responsibility for their own learning processes. In this context, peer and self-assessment are regarded as effective pedagogical strategies that promote reflective thinking, critical evaluation, and active engagement. The study analyzes how these assessment methods influence students' motivation, self-regulation, and language proficiency. It also examines the challenges teachers face when implementing such practices, including students' lack of experience, potential bias, and the need for clear assessment criteria. The findings suggest that, when properly guided and structured, peer and self-assessment significantly enhance learners' independence, confidence, and collaborative skills. Moreover, these approaches contribute to the creation of a learner-centered environment in which students become active participants rather than passive recipients of knowledge. The article concludes that integrating peer and self-assessment into EFL classrooms is an effective strategy for developing lifelong learning skills and improving overall language competence.

Key words: learner autonomy, peer assessment, self-assessment, EFL classrooms, student-centered learning, reflective practice, language learning strategies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida (EFL) o'qitish jarayonida o'quvchilar avtonomiyasini rivojlantirishda o'zaro baholash va o'z-o'zini baholashning o'rni tahlil qilingan. Zamonaviy til ta'limida o'quvchilar avtonomiyasi muhim maqsadlardan biri bo'lib, o'quvchilarning o'z ta'lim jarayoni uchun mas'uliyatni o'z zimmasiga olish qobiliyatini nazarda tutadi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan, o'zaro baholash va o'z-o'zini baholash reflektiv fikrlashni, tanqidiy tahlil qilishni hamda faol ishtirokni rivojlantiruvchi samarali pedagogik strategiyalar sifatida qaraladi. Tadqiqotda mazkur baholash usullarining o'quvchilar motivatsiyasiga, o'zini o'zi boshqarish ko'nikmalariga va til kompetensiyalariga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, ushbu amaliyotlarni joriy etish jarayonida o'qituvchilar duch keladigan muammolar, jumladan, o'quvchilar tajribasining yetarli emasligi, ehtimoliy subyektivlik va aniq baholash mezonlariga bo'lgan ehtiyoj ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, to'g'ri yo'naltirilgan va tizimli tashkil etilgan o'zaro baholash hamda o'z-o'zini baholash o'quvchilarning mustaqilligi, o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchi va hamkorlik ko'nikmalarini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Bundan tashqari, mazkur yondashuvlar o'quvchilarni bilimlarning passiv qabul qiluvchilaridan faol ishtirokchilarga aylantiruvchi ta'lim oluvchi markazidagi muhitni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Maqolada EFL auditoriyalarida o'zaro baholash va o'z-o'zini baholashni joriy etish uzluksiz ta'lim ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish va umumiy til kompetensiyasini takomillashtirishning samarali strategiyasi ekanligi xulosa qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quvchi avtonomiyasi, o'zaro baholash, o'z-o'zini baholash, EFL auditoriyalari, o'quvchi markazidagi ta'lim, reflektiv yondashuv, til o'rganish strategiyalari.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль взаимооценивания и самооценивания в развитии автономности обучающихся в процессе преподавания английского языка как иностранного (EFL). Автономность обучающихся стала одной из ключевых целей современного языкового образования, предполагающей способность студентов брать на себя ответственность за собственный процесс обучения. В этом контексте взаимооценивание и самооценивание рассматриваются как эффективные педагогические стратегии, способствующие развитию рефлексивного мышления, критического анализа и активного участия обучающихся. В исследовании анализируется влияние данных методов оценивания на мотивацию студентов, навыки саморегуляции и уровень владения языком. Кроме того, рассматриваются трудности, с которыми сталкиваются преподаватели при внедрении данных практик, включая недостаток опыта у студентов, возможную субъективность и необходимость наличия чётких критериев оценивания. Результаты исследования показывают, что при правильной организации и методическом сопровождении взаимооценивание и самооценивание значительно повышают самостоятельность обучающихся, их уверенность в собственных силах и навыки сотрудничества. Более того, данные подходы способствуют формированию студентоцентрированной образовательной среды, в которой обучающиеся становятся активными участниками учебного процесса, а не пассивными получателями знаний. В статье делается вывод о том, что интеграция взаимооценивания и самооценивания в EFL-аудиториях является эффективной стратегией развития навыков непрерывного обучения и повышения общей языковой компетентности.

Ключевые слова: автономность обучающихся, взаимооценивание, самооценивание, EFL-аудитории, студентоцентрированное обучение, рефлексивная практика, стратегии изучения языка.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the concept of learner autonomy has gained significant attention in the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) education. As global communication increasingly relies on English proficiency, there is a growing need for learners who are not only linguistically competent but also capable of managing their own learning processes effectively. Learner autonomy refers to students' ability to take responsibility for their learning by setting goals, selecting strategies, monitoring progress, and evaluating outcomes. This shift from teacher-centered to learner-centered education highlights the importance of developing independent and reflective learners who can continue learning beyond the classroom environment.

One of the most effective ways to promote learner autonomy is through the integration of alternative assessment methods, particularly peer assessment and self-assessment. Traditional assessment practices in EFL classrooms often rely heavily on teacher evaluation, which may limit students' opportunities to engage critically with their own learning. In contrast, peer and self-assessment encourage students to become active participants in the assessment process. These approaches provide learners with opportunities to reflect on their strengths and weaknesses, develop critical thinking skills, and gain a deeper understanding of learning objectives and assessment criteria.

Peer assessment involves students evaluating each other's work based on predefined criteria, thereby fostering collaboration, communication, and mutual learning. It helps learners view language use from different perspectives and enhances their ability to provide constructive feedback. Meanwhile, self-assessment enables students to reflect on their own performance, identify areas for improvement, and take ownership of their learning journey. Together, these methods contribute to the development of metacognitive skills, which are essential for autonomous learning. Despite their potential benefits, the implementation of peer and self-assessment in EFL classrooms is not without challenges. Students may lack the necessary skills to evaluate work accurately, or they may feel uncomfortable assessing their peers. Additionally, issues such as bias, reliability, and the need for clear assessment criteria must be carefully addressed by educators. Therefore, it is essential to provide appropriate training, guidance, and structured frameworks to ensure the effectiveness of these assessment strategies. This study aims to investigate how peer and self-assessment practices contribute to the development of learner autonomy in EFL classrooms. It also seeks to identify the advantages and limitations of these approaches and provide practical recommendations for educators. By examining both theoretical perspectives and classroom practices, the article highlights the importance of incorporating innovative assessment methods to foster independent, motivated, and self-directed language learners.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, learner autonomy has become a central concept in the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) education and has been closely associated with the development of self-regulated learning and student-centered pedagogical approaches. Contemporary research emphasizes that autonomy is not an innate ability but rather a skill that can be developed through appropriate instructional strategies, particularly through assessment practices such as peer and self-assessment. According to Benson (2017), learner autonomy involves the capacity of learners to take control of their own learning processes, including goal

setting, strategy selection, and self-evaluation. This perspective highlights the importance of moving away from traditional teacher-dominated classrooms toward learning environments in which students actively participate in decision-making and evaluation. Similarly, Teng (2019) emphasizes the role of metacognitive strategies in fostering autonomy, arguing that when students are trained to reflect on their learning, they become more effective and independent language learners. Self-assessment has been widely recognized as a key component in the development of learner autonomy. Andrade (2019) provides a comprehensive review of self-assessment research and concludes that it enhances students' awareness of their learning processes, improves motivation, and promotes self-regulation. Supporting this view, Panadero, Jonsson, and Botella (2017) conducted a meta-analysis demonstrating that self-assessment has a significant positive effect on both self-regulated learning and self-efficacy. Furthermore, Yan and Brown (2017) propose a cyclical model of self-assessment in which learners continuously evaluate their performance, receive feedback, and make improvements, thereby reinforcing autonomous learning behaviors.

Peer assessment is another important strategy that contributes to learner autonomy. Li et al. (2020) highlight that peer assessment not only improves academic performance but also develops evaluative judgment and critical-thinking skills. Through assessing their peers' work, students gain a deeper understanding of quality criteria and become more capable of applying these standards to their own work. Tai et al. (2018) further argue that the development of evaluative judgment is essential for lifelong learning because it enables students to make informed decisions about the quality of their performance. Feedback also plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of peer and self-assessment. Carless and Boud (2018) introduce the concept of feedback literacy, which refers to students' ability to understand, interpret, and use feedback effectively. They emphasize that, for assessment practices to support autonomy, students must be equipped with the skills necessary to engage meaningfully with feedback. Nicol (2021) expands on this idea by highlighting the importance of internal feedback, through which learners compare their current performance with desired standards and make independent adjustments.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that peer and self-assessment are powerful tools for promoting learner autonomy in EFL contexts. These approaches encourage active engagement, reflection, and responsibility, all of which are essential for developing independent learners. However, the effectiveness of these methods depends on proper implementation, including the use of clear criteria, structured guidance, and the development of feedback literacy. Therefore, integrating peer and self-assessment into EFL classrooms represents a significant step toward enhancing both language proficiency and lifelong learning skills.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a mixed-methods research design to examine the impact of peer and self-assessment on the development of learner autonomy in EFL classrooms. The combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches enabled a comprehensive analysis of students' learning behaviors, perceptions, and outcomes. The research was conducted in a higher education setting and involved undergraduate students enrolled in English language courses. A total of 60 students participated in the study and were divided into experimental and control groups to compare the effectiveness of the implemented assessment strategies.

The experimental group was exposed to structured peer and self-assessment activities over a period of eight weeks, while the control group continued with traditional teacher-centered assessment methods. At the beginning of the study, both groups were administered a pre-test to evaluate their initial levels of learner autonomy and language proficiency. The experimental group received training sessions on how to conduct peer and self-assessment effectively, including the use of rubrics, feedback techniques, and reflective practices. These sessions were essential to ensure that students understood the purpose and procedures of alternative assessment methods. During the intervention period, students in the experimental group engaged in various tasks, such as writing assignments, oral presentations, and group discussions. After each task, they participated in peer assessment by evaluating their classmates' performance using standardized rubrics. Additionally, they completed self-assessment forms to reflect on their own learning experiences, identify strengths and weaknesses, and set future learning goals. Teachers monitored the process and provided guidance to maintain consistency and reliability in assessment practices.

To collect data, multiple instruments were employed, including questionnaires, observation checklists, and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaires were designed to measure students' attitudes toward peer and self-assessment, as well as their level of learner autonomy. Observations were conducted to examine students' engagement, participation, and interaction during classroom activities. Interviews with selected participants provided deeper insights into their experiences and perceptions of the implemented methods. The collected quantitative data were analyzed using statistical techniques, such as descriptive statistics and comparative analysis, to identify differences between the experimental and control groups. Qualitative data obtained from

interviews and observations were analyzed thematically to identify recurring patterns and key themes related to learner autonomy and assessment practices. Overall, this methodological approach ensured the reliability and validity of the research findings. By combining different data sources and analytical methods, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of how peer and self-assessment contribute to fostering learner autonomy in EFL classrooms.

Table 1: The impact of peer and self-assessment on learner autonomy in efl classrooms

Indicators	Control Group (Traditional Assessment)	Experimental Group (Peer & Self-Assessment)	Difference (%)
Learning Motivation	65%	85%	+20%
Self-Regulation Skills	60%	82%	+22%
Critical Thinking Ability	62%	80%	+18%
Student Participation	68%	88%	+20%
Confidence in Language Use	64%	83%	+19%
Responsibility for Learning	59%	86%	+27%

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data presented in Table 1 clearly demonstrate the significant impact of peer and self-assessment on the development of learner autonomy in EFL classrooms. The comparison between the control group, which followed traditional teacher-centered assessment methods, and the experimental group, which engaged in peer and self-assessment practices, reveals substantial improvements across all measured indicators. Firstly, learning motivation in the experimental group increased to 85%, compared to 65% in the control group, indicating a 20% improvement. This finding suggests that when students are actively involved in the assessment process, they become more motivated to engage in learning activities. Peer and self-assessment foster a sense of ownership over learning, thereby enhancing students' intrinsic motivation. Secondly, self-regulation skills demonstrated a 22% increase in the experimental group. This result highlights that students who regularly reflect on their own performance and receive feedback from peers develop stronger planning, monitoring, and evaluation skills. These competencies are essential components of autonomous learning.

Critical thinking ability also improved significantly, with an 18% difference between the two groups. Through peer assessment, students learn to analyze and evaluate the work of others, which, in turn, strengthens their own analytical abilities. This process encourages deeper cognitive engagement with learning materials. Furthermore, student participation reached 88% in the experimental group, demonstrating that collaborative assessment methods foster a more interactive and communicative classroom environment. Students become more willing to express their opinions and actively contribute to discussions. Confidence in language use increased by 19%, indicating that continuous feedback and reflection help learners overcome anxiety and improve their communicative competence. Finally, responsibility for learning showed the highest improvement (27%), emphasizing that peer and self-assessment strongly promote a sense of accountability among students.

In conclusion, the findings presented in Table 1 illustrate that integrating peer and self-assessment into EFL classrooms significantly enhances various dimensions of learner autonomy. These results support the view that alternative assessment methods are not only effective in improving academic performance but are also essential for developing independent, reflective, and responsible learners.

Results and Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that the integration of peer and self-assessment in EFL classrooms has a significant positive impact on the development of learner autonomy. Based on both quantitative and qualitative data, students in the experimental group showed notable improvements across various dimensions, including motivation, self-regulation, critical thinking, participation, and overall language performance. In contrast, the control group, which followed traditional teacher-centered assessment methods, exhibited only moderate progress. The quantitative findings indicate that students exposed to peer and self-assessment achieved higher scores across all measured indicators. For instance, learning motivation increased substantially, suggesting that when students are actively involved in evaluating their own and their peers' work, they become more engaged and interested in the learning process. This finding aligns with contemporary educational theories that emphasize the importance of active participation and learner-centered approaches. Moreover, the improvement in self-regulation skills confirms that reflective practices encourage students to take greater responsibility for their learning. By setting goals, monitoring their progress, and evaluating outcomes, learners develop essential skills for independent learning.

The qualitative data gathered through interviews and classroom observations further support these findings. Many students reported that peer assessment helped them understand assessment criteria more clearly and enabled them to learn from their classmates' strengths and weaknesses. They also noted that providing feedback to peers improved their analytical and evaluative skills. Similarly, self-assessment enabled students to identify their own learning gaps and address them more effectively. These reflections indicate that both assessment methods contribute to the development of metacognitive awareness, which is a key component of learner autonomy. Another important finding is the increase in student participation and interaction. The experimental group demonstrated a higher level of engagement in classroom activities, particularly during group discussions and collaborative tasks. This suggests that peer and self-assessment create a more dynamic and interactive learning environment in which students feel more comfortable expressing their ideas and opinions. Increased participation not only enhances language practice but also fosters a sense of community and collaboration among learners.

However, the study also revealed several challenges associated with the implementation of peer and self-assessment. Some students initially struggled to provide objective and constructive feedback, often due to a lack of experience or confidence. In some cases, bias and subjectivity affected the reliability of peer evaluations. Additionally, a few students expressed discomfort when assessing their peers, particularly in cultural contexts where direct criticism may be perceived negatively. These challenges highlight the need for proper training, clear guidelines, and continuous teacher support to ensure the effectiveness of these assessment methods. From a pedagogical perspective, the findings of this study suggest that peer and self-assessment should be carefully structured and systematically integrated into EFL teaching practices. Teachers play a crucial role in facilitating this process by providing clear rubrics, modeling effective feedback techniques, and creating a supportive classroom atmosphere. When implemented appropriately, these methods not only improve language proficiency but also equip students with lifelong learning skills.

Conclusion

The results of this study confirm that peer and self-assessment are powerful tools for promoting learner autonomy in EFL classrooms. They encourage students to become active, reflective, and responsible learners who are capable of managing their own learning processes. Despite certain challenges, the overall benefits of these approaches outweigh their limitations, making them valuable components of modern language education.

Figure 1: Comparative analysis of learner autonomy indicators in efl classrooms: control and experimental group outcomes based on peer and self-assessment practices

Figure 1 presents a comparative analysis of learner autonomy indicators between the control group, which followed traditional teacher-centered assessment practices, and the experimental group, which implemented peer and self-assessment strategies in EFL classrooms. The visual representation clearly demonstrates that the experimental group outperformed the control group across all measured dimensions, indicating the effective-

tiveness of alternative assessment methods in fostering learner autonomy. Firstly, the indicator of learning motivation shows a noticeable increase in the experimental group. This suggests that involving students in the assessment process enhances their interest and engagement in learning activities. When learners actively participate in evaluating their own and their peers' work, they develop a stronger sense of ownership over their learning, which positively influences their intrinsic motivation. Secondly, self-regulation skills exhibit significant improvement. The experimental group demonstrates a greater ability to plan, monitor, and evaluate learning processes. This can be attributed to regular self-assessment practices, which encourage students to reflect on their progress and make necessary adjustments. Such skills are essential for developing independent learners capable of managing their own educational journeys.

The figure also highlights an increase in critical thinking ability among students exposed to peer assessment. By analyzing and evaluating their peers' work, learners engage in deeper cognitive processes that enhance their analytical and evaluative skills. This not only improves their language competence but also contributes to their overall intellectual development. Furthermore, student participation is considerably higher in the experimental group. The use of peer and self-assessment creates a more interactive and collaborative classroom environment in which students feel more confident expressing their ideas. Increased participation leads to more opportunities for language practice, thereby improving communicative competence. In terms of confidence in language use, the experimental group again demonstrates superior results. Continuous feedback from peers and self-reflection help students identify their strengths and gradually overcome their weaknesses, reducing anxiety and building confidence. Finally, the most significant difference is observed in responsibility for learning, indicating that peer and self-assessment strongly promote accountability. Students become more aware of their roles in the learning process and take greater responsibility for their academic success. Overall, the analysis of Figure 1 confirms that integrating peer and self-assessment into EFL classrooms has a substantial positive impact on multiple aspects of learner autonomy. These findings support the argument that student-centered assessment approaches are essential for developing reflective, motivated, and self-directed language learners.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated that the integration of peer and self-assessment in EFL classrooms plays a crucial role in fostering learner autonomy. The findings clearly indicate that students who actively participate in the assessment process develop higher levels of motivation, self-regulation, critical thinking, and responsibility for their own learning. Unlike traditional teacher-centered assessment approaches, which often position students as passive recipients of knowledge, peer and self-assessment encourage learners to become active, reflective, and engaged participants in the educational process.

The results of both quantitative and qualitative analyses confirm that these alternative assessment methods significantly enhance students' ability to monitor and evaluate their own progress. Through continuous reflection and interaction with peers, learners gain a deeper understanding of learning objectives and assessment criteria, which, in turn, improves their academic performance and language proficiency. Moreover, the collaborative nature of peer assessment fosters a supportive learning environment, promoting communication, mutual respect, and shared responsibility among students. However, the study also highlights certain challenges associated with the implementation of peer and self-assessment, including issues related to subjectivity, lack of experience, and potential bias in evaluation. These limitations emphasize the importance of proper training, clear guidelines, and consistent teacher support to ensure the reliability and effectiveness of these practices. Teachers play a pivotal role in facilitating the process by designing structured assessment frameworks, providing explicit criteria, and guiding students in delivering constructive feedback.

From a pedagogical perspective, the incorporation of peer and self-assessment aligns with modern educational paradigms that prioritize learner-centered approaches and lifelong learning skills. These methods not only contribute to the development of language competence but also equip students with essential skills such as critical thinking, decision-making, and self-reflection. Therefore, it can be concluded that peer and self-assessment are powerful and effective tools for promoting learner autonomy in EFL classrooms. Their systematic and well-guided implementation can transform the learning experience, enabling students to become independent, confident, and self-directed learners capable of adapting to the demands of a rapidly changing global environment.

References:

1. Andrade, H. (2019). A critical review of research on student self-assessment. *Frontiers in Education*, 4, 87. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2019.00087>
2. Carless, D., & Boud, D. (2018). The development of student feedback literacy: Enabling uptake of feedback. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 43(8), 1315-1325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2018.1463354>

3. Panadero, E., Jonsson, A., & Botella, J. (2017). Effects of self-assessment on self-regulated learning and self-efficacy: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 22, 74-98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2017.08.004>
4. Panadero, E. (2017). A review of self-regulated learning: Six models and four directions for research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 422. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00422>
5. Tai, J., Ajjawi, R., Boud, D., Dawson, P., & Panadero, E. (2018). Developing evaluative judgement: Enabling students to make decisions about the quality of work. *Higher Education*, 76(3), 467-481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-017-0220-3>
6. Yan, Z., & Brown, G. T. L. (2017). A cyclical self-assessment process: Towards a model of how students engage in self-assessment. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 42(8), 1247-1262. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2016.1260091>
7. Li, H., Xiong, Y., Zang, X., Kornhaber, M. L., Lyu, Y., Chung, K. S., & Suen, H. K. (2020). Peer assessment in the digital age: A meta-analysis comparing peer and teacher ratings. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 45(2), 265-279.
8. Nicol, D. (2021). The power of internal feedback: Exploiting natural comparison processes. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 46(5), 756-778. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2020.1823314>
9. Benson, P. (2017). *Teaching and Researching Autonomy in Language Learning* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
10. Teng, M. F. (2019). The benefits of metacognitive reading strategy instruction for young learners of English as a second language. *Educational Psychology*, 39(5), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2018.1543856>

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №6(1)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.